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Neuropedagogika: ta'limda neyrofiziologik yondashuvlarning ahamiyati

Asqarova Umida Abdukamol qizi¹, Zaripova Dilnoza Anvarovna²

¹*Al-Xorazmiy nomidagi Toshkent Axborot Texnologiyalari Universiteti*

AKT sohasida KT yo'nalishi magistratura bosqich talabasi

²*Al-Xorazmiy nomidagi Toshkent Axborot Texnologiyalari Universiteti, PhD, dotsent*

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada neuropedagogika fanining zamonaviy ta'lim tizimidagi o'rni va uning amaliy ahamiyati yoritilgan. Neuropedagogika – bu neyrofiziologiya, psixologiya va pedagogika fanlari integratsiyasi asosida shakllangan, inson miyasi faoliyatini o'rganish orqali ta'lim jarayonini optimallashtirishga xizmat qiluvchi ilmiy yo'nalishdir. Maqolada ushbu yo'nalishning asosiy nazariy tamoyillari, jumladan individual kognitiv farqlarni hisobga olish, multimodal ta'lim texnologiyalarini qo'llash, emotsional muhitning ta'siri va miyaning rivojlanish bosqichlarini inobatga olish zarurati tahlil qilinadi. Shuningdek, ta'limda neuropedagogik yondashuvlardan foydalanishning amaliy samaralari – o'quvchilarning diqqatini jamlash, bilimni chuqurroq o'zlashtirish va stressni kamaytirish kabi natijalar ham yoritilgan. Maqola zamonaviy ta'limda shaxsga yo'naltirilgan, samaradorlikni oshirishga qaratilgan uslublarni joriy etishda neuropedagogikaning ahamiyatini ilmiy asosda ko'rsatib beradi.

Kalit so'zlar: neuropedagogika, neyrofiziologiya, ta'lim, miyaning plastiklik xususiyati, individual yondashuv, kognitiv faoliyat, multimodal ta'lim, emotsional muhit, o'quv motivatsiyasi, zamonaviy ta'lim, pedagogik innovatsiyalar.

Нейропедагогика: значение нейрофизиологических подходов в образовании

Аскарова Умида Абдукамол кызы¹, Зарипова Дилноза Анваровна²

¹*Ташкентский университет информационных технологий имени Ал-Хоразми*

Магистрант направления ПО в ИКТ

²*Ташкентский университет информационных технологий имени Аль-Хоразми, PhD, доцент*

Аннотация. В статье рассматривается роль нейропедагогика в современной системе образования и ее практическое значение. Нейропедагогика — научное направление, сформированное на основе интеграции нейрофизиологии, психологии и педагогики, призванное оптимизировать образовательный процесс посредством изучения функционирования человеческого мозга. В статье анализируются основные теоретические положения данного направления, в том числе необходимость учета индивидуальных когнитивных различий, использования мультимодальных образовательных технологий, влияния эмоциональной среды, этапов развития мозга. Также

подчеркиваются практические преимущества использования нейропедагогических подходов в образовании, такие как улучшение концентрации внимания учащихся, более глубокое обучение и снижение стресса. В статье научно обоснована важность нейропедагогики во внедрении личностно-ориентированных, повышающих эффективность методов в современное образование.

Ключевые слова: нейропедагогика, нейрофизиология, образование, пластичность мозга, индивидуальный подход, познавательная деятельность, мультимодальное образование, эмоциональная среда, мотивация обучения, современное образование, педагогические инновации.

Neuropedagogy: the importance of neurophysiological approaches in education

Askarova Umida Abdukamol kyzy¹, Zaripova Dilnoza Anvarovna²

¹Tashkent University of Information Technologies named after Al-Khwarizmi
Master's student in the VE in ICT

²Tashkent University of Information Technologies named after Al-Khwarizmi, PhD, Associate Professor

Abstract. The article discusses the role of neuropedagogy in the modern education system and its practical significance. Neuropedagogy is a scientific direction formed on the basis of the integration of neurophysiology, psychology and pedagogy, designed to optimize the educational process by studying the functioning of the human brain. The article analyzes the main theoretical provisions of this direction, including the need to take into account individual cognitive differences, the use of multimodal educational technologies, the influence of the emotional environment, and the stages of brain development. It also emphasizes the practical benefits of using neuropedagogical approaches in education, such as improving students' concentration, deeper learning and reducing stress. The article scientifically substantiates the importance of neuropedagogy in the implementation of personality-oriented, efficiency-enhancing methods in modern education.

Keywords: neuropedagogy, neurophysiology, education, brain plasticity, individual approach, cognitive activity, multimodal education, emotional environment, motivation for learning, modern education, pedagogical innovations.

Kirish

XXI asrda inson miyasi va tafakkur jarayonlarini chuqur o'rganishga qaratilgan fanlar taraqqiyoti ta'lim sohasida yangi yondashuvlarning shakllanishiga olib keldi. Ana shunday yondashuvlardan biri — neuropedagogika — miya faoliyatining pedagogik jarayonlarga ta'sirini o'rganadigan va o'quv jarayonini neyrobiologik asosda tashkil etishga qaratilgan ilmiy yo'nalishdir. Bu yondashuv o'quvchilarning individual kognitiv xususiyatlariga asoslangan ta'lim strategiyalarini ishlab chiqish imkonini beradi.

Neuropedagogikaning ilmiy asoslari

Neuropedagogika neyrofiziologiya (miya va asab tizimi faoliyatini o'rganish), kognitiv psixologiya (idrok, xotira, diqqat jarayonlari) va zamonaviy pedagogikaning integratsiyasi natijasida shakllangan. Asosiy g'oya — o'quvchilarning bilimni qanday qabul qilishi, saqlashi va qo'llashi jarayonlarini miya faoliyati bilan bog'liq holda tahlil qilishdir.

Tadqiqotlar shuni ko'rsatadiki, miyaning plastiklik (ya'ni, yangi neyron aloqalarni hosil qilish qobiliyati) xususiyati doimiy o'rganish jarayonida faollashadi. Bu esa mos pedagogik yondashuvlar orqali o'quvchilarning salohiyatini to'liq ochish imkonini beradi.

Neuropedagogikaning asosiy tamoyillari

1. Individual kognitiv farqlarni hisobga olish. Har bir o'quvchining miyasi ma'lumotni qabul qilish va qayta ishlash jihatidan o'ziga xosdir. Shu sababli standartlashtirilgan yondashuv o'rniga moslashtirilgan, diferensial ta'lim afzallik kasb etadi.

2. Multimodal ta'lim texnologiyalari. Vizual (ko'rish), audial (eshitish), kinestetik (harakat orqali) ta'lim usullarini uyg'unlashtirish orqali miya faoliyatini rag'batlantirish mumkin.

3. Emotsional fondning ahamiyati. Miyada yangi ma'lumotlarni qayta ishlash jarayoni emotsional holat bilan bevosita bog'liq. Ijobiy ruhiy muhit o'quv jarayonining samaradorligini oshiradi.

4. Miyaning rivojlanish bosqichlarini hisobga olish. Yoshga qarab neyron aloqalarning shakllanish tezligi va kuchi farqlanadi. Shunga mos metodikalar tanlanishi zarur.

Amaliyotda qo'llanilishi va natijalar

Neuropedagogika yondashuvlari asosida tashkil etilgan ta'lim jarayoni quyidagi ijobiy natijalarni beradi:

O'quvchilarning diqqat va xotira ko'rsatkichlari yaxshilanadi;

Kognitiv jarayonlar (o'rganish, tushunish, xulosa chiqarish) faollashadi;

Shaxsiylashtirilgan yondashuv orqali o'quvchining mustaqil fikrlash qobiliyati rivojlanadi;

Emotsional muvozanat saqlanadi, stress darajasi kamayadi.

Amaliy misol sifatida, o'quv darslariga qisqa meditatsiyalar, neyro-o'yinlar yoki fokuslangan mashqlarni kiritish, talabalar e'tiborini tiklashda foydali bo'lishi isbotlangan.

Xulosa

Neuropedagogika – bu zamonaviy ta'lim tizimini chuqur ilmiy asosda tashkil etish imkonini beruvchi fanlararo yo'nalishdir. U o'quvchilarning miyaviy va

psixologik faoliyatini chuqur tahlil etish orqali ta'lim sifatini oshirish, pedagogik metodikalarni takomillashtirish va shaxsiy rivojlanishni qo'llab

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Адрес: 150100, Ферганская область, г. Фергана, ул. Солима, 23/4, кв. 26

E-mail: chief_editor@rai-journal.uz

Сайт: <https://rai-journal.uz/>

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Address: 150100, Fergana region, Fergana city, Solima street, 23/4, apt. 26

E-mail: chief_editor@rai-journal.uz

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